

Preventative conservation of large scale industrial objects – the Victorian steamship *Great Britain*

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Introduction

The Victorian steamship *Great Britain* is one of the world's most significant historic vessels. The ship is notable as being the first ship to combine innovations that are now commonplace, such as a metal hull, engine, and screw propeller. When she was built, she was the largest ship in the world, and she later went on to become famous in the Australian emigrant trade and as a troopship in the Crimean War. In 1970, after great effort and expense, her rusting wrought iron hulk was salvaged from the Falkland Islands in a dramatic rescue and towed across the Atlantic to her original 'birthplace' in Bristol.

There, she was opened to the public, and a program of restoration was started. The approach followed was typical of that found with most historic ships, namely, to bring her back to one defined period in her life, disregarding other periods, and to treat preservation of the ship in the same manner as a modern, working ship. Thus, if an iron hull plate was badly corroded, it was cut out and replaced with modern steel plate. If electricity was needed on the ship, a hole was cut through the hull to run the cabling. The process of gradual replacement of corroded original elements of the ship's hull saw a dramatic loss in original material over the years and the distinction between what was original and what was new was in danger of becoming blurred.

After 30 years of this treatment - scraping rust, sandblasting, and painting - the ship was still visibly and rapidly corroding. Visitor numbers fell, and with them, revenue for maintenance. In common with many historic ships and industrial objects, the ship was in a downward cycle, with the root cause being the difficulty and cost of conservation. Eura's conservators estimated in 1998 that the vessel could eventually suffer a total structural failure and collapse within about 20 years.

In 1998, however, the UK's Heritage Lottery Fund provided support to commission a conservation-based approach to future management of ship. The work that followed lasted 6 years, and cost over 19 million Euros.

Initial conservation research

The scope of the conservation work was established by a Conservation Plan. This plan was in two elements: Part 1 identified the surviving fabric within the ship and dockyard, and evaluated the cultural significance of each element. It then laid out a number of conservation policies which were designed to retain the significance identified in the evaluation. Part

2 evaluated the condition of the ship and gave options for preserving the ship.

After establishing a documentary and nomenclature system within the ship, which allowed individual parts of the ship to be identified and described with precision, conservators from Eura Conservation mapped the extent of corrosion within the hull of the ship, and the level of chlorides within corrosion products. A high level of chloride contamination was evident in the lower hull, suggesting similar contamination within the parent metal. The upper exterior of the hull was photogrammetrically recorded, and an electronic survey of the entire hull and drydock allowed creation of a three dimensional CAD model, which was later to used to support the engineering and architectural support work.

The mix of corrosion products, acting in combination with high relative humidity in the ship's drydock and soluble chloride acting as an electrolyte, produced an active electro-chemical corrosion sequence. To prevent the corrosion, at least one of the agents of decay would have to be removed or negated. A range of options was investigated to achieve this, including aqueous washing, alkaline sulphite treatment; sodium hydroxide treatment; alkali washes; electrolysis; hydrogen reduction; inhibitors; cathodic protection; and desiccation. These were assessed according to their ability to fulfill the following criteria:

1. Long term retention of original material from the ship's working life;
2. Minimal intervention and reversibility of treatment;
3. Cost: This was assessed in terms of the estimated magnitude of the capital equipment required, the running costs, and the maintenance effort required;
4. Effectiveness of treatment in halting corrosion;
5. Effect of treatment on accessibility and presentation of the vessel to the public

The only options that allowed for long life expectancy were those that controlled the ship's environment. Drying the environment around the hull was the only feasible alternative within those options. It was to prove to be a technically challenging task that involved constructing an envelope around the ship and controlling the relative humidity within the space.

Experimentation

In order to make judgements on the design and operation of the controlled storage space around the hull, conservation scientists from Cardiff University experimentally examined the iron corrosion process, to establish the corrosion reactions that would occur as the metal dried, and to determine the effect of relative humidity on these reactions. Corrosion products known to exist in the hull were synthesised, and experiments were conducted in low humidity environments to examine the effects of these materials on pure iron powder in a climatic chamber. Analysis revealed the presence of three main corrosion products. At very low relative humidity levels β -FeOOH was found, becoming active above 15 percent RH, and also forming as a by-product of other corrosion processes. Extrapolation from survey data indicated however, that little of this product was likely to be present in the ship.

At 19% RH it was found that $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dihydrate ferrous chloride took over as the most stable form of hydrate, but this form did not corrode the

test samples. By contrast, tetrahydrate ferrous chloride ($\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was the most stable form of hydrate at 22% RH. Because there is extra water in the tetrahydrate, it supports electrolytic corrosion and corrodes iron in contact with it. Consequently, slow corrosion occurred at 25% RH and rapid corrosion at 30%.

The conservation team thus recognised that to prevent the tetrahydrate from corroding the ship's iron, relative humidity had to be lowered to 20% so that the only the dihydrate would form.

The conservation design

Whilst conservation scientists were addressing the chemistry of corrosion, a team of architects and engineers was designing the controlled environment around the hull. This was determined by a range of financial, technical, and aesthetic considerations. Various structures were considered that would entirely encase the hull. The solution was instead to construct a horizontal water-covered glass plate around the hull, creating a seal at the ship's waterline. This plate extends from the hull to the edge of the drydock, and created a controlled environment within the ship and below the glass on the exterior of the hull.

The plate is constructed from 169 laminated glass panels, each weighing around 400kg, supported by horizontal steel joists and glass beams. The surface area of around 1000 square metres is covered in 50mm of continuously flowing water, which keeps the surface clean and the temperature cool, while also giving visitors the impression that the ship is afloat. Within the drydock and within the ship local desiccation of the hull iron occurs by means of two gas-operated dehumidifiers which feed dehydrated air over the surface.

The design of the glass plate incorporated stair and elevator access, to allow visitors to descend 'beneath the water' to walk alongside the submerged hull. In addition to desiccating the hull, the dehumidification machinery thus also had to cater for moisture load from visitors, and the fresh air they need. The dehumidifiers also deal with door opening, water leakage into the dry dock, and leakage through the hull.

Treatment of the upper external hull

Sampling of chlorides from the upper external hull above the waterline demonstrated that there was little contamination in this area. The decision was therefore made that the upper hull could be adequately cleaned by mechanical methods and protected by a painted coating system.

Two approaches were adopted for cleaning. 80 percent of the upper hull was robust enough to be hydro-blasted with pure water at up to 2500 bar, cleaning the iron to SA2.5. This standard was that which was necessary to guarantee paint adhesion. The remaining 20% was too fragile for hydro-blasting, and was instead cleaned at 8 bar using a 'vacublast' and garnet powder choice. The metal was coated with a two-part zinc-rich wet application epoxy primer, a mid coat of two-part epoxy, and a two-part conservation-grade urethane sheen finish. This system combined the good chemical resistance of epoxy resins with the UV resistance of polyurethanes.

Hull strengthening system

Within the hull, finite element analysis revealed weakening of the frames and deck beams. The solution was to bridge gaps in the structure using new steel frame splints. These were attached to the hull using a hierarchy of intervention - existing bolt and rivet holes were used in preference, then stainless clamping systems. No iron could be cut or welded without written permission, and every element introduced into the ship was to be completely reversible. Where these supports and splints are visible to the public, they are left on open display but are painted a different colour to distinguish them from the original structure. The same hierarchy was used for all construction work in and around the dock and its buildings. The hierarchy gave contractors an agreed set of rules within which they could work, and assured the ship's owners that no historic or culturally significant material would be destroyed.

Applicability of current work to other objects

As with all conservation work, that performed on the *Great Britain* had to balance cost, technical feasibility, visitor access and aesthetics. While the costs of sustaining the controlled environment are high, the conservation work has, however, provided a period of time in which the ship's corrosion has been slowed dramatically.

The corrosion research findings attained to date have already been disseminated in conservation science literature. The results should be applicable to storage of iron in museums around the world, and will give museums information on how to store artefacts at a specific humidity and how to care for them if conditions change.

The creation of a large external controlled environment, and the non-destructive ship structural strengthening splint system are both applicable to other large scale projects dealing with historic objects of an equivalent level of significance.

Perhaps the most important legacy of the project was the successful application of conservation management planning. This gave the ship's conservators confidence in identifying original ship fabric, and assessing each element's historical and cultural significance. It established a clear way of determining the merit of different conservation and maintenance strategies, such that priorities could be established and scarce financial and human resources could be directed where they were most needed. It also recognised that the conservation work had to be accompanied by creation of a sustainable visitor attraction, which would generate sufficient revenue to fund future maintenance. Without the guidance provided by the conservation management plan, the ship would not have been saved.